

EELISA

European University

Network of Open Science Ambassadors

Task: 3.5. Development of EELISA Network of OS Ambassadors

Date: July 2023 (updated May 2024)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Development of the EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors

Final Version

Technical references

Grant Agreement number:	101035811
Project Acronym:	EELISA InnoCORE
Project title:	EELISA INNOVation and Common Research strategy
Start date of the project:	1 June 2021
Duration of the project:	36 months

Deliverable No.:	D3.6
Work Package:	WP3
Task:	3.5. Development of EELISA Network of OS Ambassadors
Lead beneficiary:	University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest
Due date of deliverable:	May 2024
Actual submission date:	2024-05-29
Dissemination level:	

Document history

V	Date	WP Leader	Reviewed by:
0.1	2024-05-10	UNSTPB	First draft, Dana Gheorghe, Loredana Manasia, , Catalin Negru
0.2	2024-05-21	ITU	First quality check, Hür Bersam Sidal Bolat, Burcu Bulut
0.3	2024-05-24	UPM	Second quality check, Juan Manuel Muñoz-Guijosa
0.4	2024-05-24	UNSTPB	Final version, Dana Gheorghe, Loredana Manasia, , Catalin Negru

Contents

<i>Executive summary</i>	9
<i>Introduction</i>	10
SECTION 1. The OS Ambassador Blueprint: A Guide to Effective Recruitment and Active Engagement	12
1. Identifying Potential OS Ambassadors	13
A Commitment to Open Science	13
Leadership Potential and Ability to Inspire Others	13
Expertise	13
Diversity: A Key Ingredient	14
Process of Identification	14
2. The Recruitment Process	15
Setting Clear Expectations	15
Inviting Applications.....	16
Evaluation and Selection.....	16
Appointment Period and Network Enrichment	16
Providing a Platform for Engagement.....	16
3. Roles and Responsibilities of an OS Ambassador	17
Advocacy	17
Education	18
Support	20
Community Building	21
4. Effective Training and Support for OS Ambassadors	23
Initial Induction: Open Science Principles and Best Practices	23
Continuous Learning Opportunities	23
Implementation of a Mentorship or Peer-Support Program.....	24
Provision of Essential Resources, Tools, and Platforms.....	24
Institutional Support and Recognition	24
5. Strategies for Active Engagement	24
Creating a Regular Events Calendar	25
Developing Individualized Outreach Plans	25
Fostering Collaboration among University Stakeholders	25
Exchange Programs within EELISA	26
6. Evaluation and Feedback	26
Objective Evaluation Criteria	27
Regular Reviews and Feedback.....	27
Enriching the Network	28
SECTION 2. The EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors	29
7. The Process of creating the OS Network of Ambassadors	30

Timeline and milestones.....	30
Presentation of the EELISA Network of OS Ambassadors	32
8. Work Plan for Implementing Outreach Actions	37
9. Dissemination and sustainability activities.....	57
Communication of the OS Network	57
Leveraging the Open Science Training Hub: A Resource for OS Ambassadors	59
Continuation of the OS Network of Ambassadors under EELISA 2.0	61
11. Concluding Remarks	63

List of Figures and Tables

Figure 1. Dimensions of OS Ambassadors training and support	23
Figure 2. Recommended strategies for OSA engagement	25
Figure 6. Components of the Evaluation and Feedback Mechanism	27
Figure 3. Evolution of the OS Network of Ambassadors	30
Figure 4. The gender distribution of the OS Ambassadors	32
Figure 5. Presentation of the OS Ambassadors work plan components	38
Figure 7. The homepage of the EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors	57
Figure 8. Post on social media about the Network	58
Figure 9. EELISA OS Network of Ambassadors Video	59
Figure 10. The homepage of the EELISA Open Science Catalogue	60
Figure 11. Examples of courses available in the OS Course Catalogue	60
Figure 12. Possible synergies with EELISA 2.0.....	62
Table 1. Responsibilities associated with the advocacy role	17
Table 2. Responsibilities associated with the education role	19
Table 3. Responsibilities associated with the support role.....	20
Table 4. Responsibilities associated with the community building role	22
Table 5. The EELISA Network of OS Ambassadors.....	33
Table 6. T1 Actions - Connect and Collaborate.....	40
Table 7. T2: Represent and Advocate.....	43
Table 8. T3 Actions: Dialogue & Persuade.....	47
Table 9. T4 Actions - Train & Empower.....	51

Executive summary

This document outlines a framework and specific actions for developing and implementing the EELISA Network of Open Science (OS) Ambassadors. It is divided into two main sections, providing a detailed guide for recruiting, training, engaging, and supporting OS Ambassadors, as well as presenting the collective efforts of the EELISA network.

The first section, "The OS Ambassador Blueprint: A Guide to Effective Recruitment and Active Engagement," is designed to assist EELISA InnoCORE universities in effectively identifying, recruiting, training, and engaging OS Ambassadors. It begins with strategies for recognizing potential ambassadors who are committed to Open Science principles, possess leadership potential, and bring diverse perspectives. It then details a systematic recruitment process, outlining the steps for engaging, interviewing, and onboarding candidates with clear expectations and a supportive environment.

The roles and responsibilities of OS Ambassadors are elaborated, emphasizing their advocacy, education, support, and community-building functions. The guide also highlights effective training and support mechanisms, including comprehensive induction, continuous learning opportunities, mentorship programs, and the provision of essential resources. Practical strategies for maintaining long-term engagement, such as regular events, tailored outreach plans, and fostering collaboration, are presented. Additionally, the importance of regular evaluation and feedback is stressed to enhance the performance and impact of OS Ambassadors.

The second section, "The EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors," focuses on the establishment and activities of the OS Ambassadors network. It discusses the timeline and milestones involved in creating the network, highlighting the collaborative efforts and significant achievements. A detailed work plan is provided, developed by the ambassadors, which categorizes tasks and actions aimed at effective communication, outreach, and sustainability. The document also outlines dissemination and sustainability activities, emphasizing communication actions and potential connections to EELISA 2.0 to ensure the network's long-term viability.

In summary, this document establishes a comprehensive framework designed to cultivate a robust Open Science culture across EELISA universities. By implementing the strategies delineated in the OS Ambassador Blueprint and capitalizing on the collaborative efforts of the EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors, the consortium is poised to significantly enhance the impact of scientific research and innovation.

Introduction

Task 3.5, "Development of EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors (OSAN)," is an ambitious activity within EELISA InnoCORE WP3. Created and launched as an informal structure, it now works to raise awareness on open science matters. Championing a shared vision of transforming the way scientific knowledge is conducted and shared in Europe, OSAN aims to foster a more open, collaborative, and beneficial scientific landscape.

The **D3.6 deliverable, "Development of the EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors,"** is organized into two primary sections which follow the stages that led to the creation and operation of OSAN, along with a significant milestone achieved on this journey: "The OS Ambassador Blueprint: A Guide to Effective Recruitment and Active Engagement" and "The EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors." These sections have been combined to comprehensively reflect the process and support subsequent actions, thereby facilitating the transfer of best practices to other universities. The first section, the blueprint, was finalized in the summer of 2023 and served as a foundational reference for establishing the network of ambassadors.

Section 1: The OS Ambassador Blueprint: A Guide to Effective Recruitment and Active Engagement

This section has been developed to assist EELISA InnoCORE universities in effectively identifying, recruiting, training, engaging, and assessing the Open Science (OS) Ambassadors. Open Science introduces a novel approach to scientific inquiry, emphasizing cooperative work and the dissemination of knowledge through digital technologies and collaborative tools. Positioned at the forefront of this transformative movement, universities are pivotal in harnessing their vast knowledge resources and the talents of their students and faculty. This section presents the process of initiating and maintaining a successful OS Ambassador program within the EELISA InnoCORE network and beyond. The structure of this section is as follows:

- **Chapter 1: Identifying Potential OS Ambassadors** offers universities insights into recognizing potential ambassadors among their students and faculty who possess the necessary skills and enthusiasm to advocate for Open Science.
- **Chapter 2: The Recruitment Process** details an approach for engaging, interviewing, and onboarding these candidates.
- **Chapter 3: Roles and Responsibilities of an OS Ambassador** clarifies the expectations universities should have of these ambassadors, providing a framework for their roles.
- **Chapter 4: Effective Training and Support for OS Ambassadors** outlines strategies for ensuring ambassadors are well-prepared to fulfill their roles effectively.
- **Chapter 5: Strategies for Active Engagement** presents practical approaches for universities to maintain long-term ambassador involvement and sustain their enthusiasm.
- **Chapter 6: Evaluation and Feedback** emphasizes the importance of universities regularly assessing ambassador performance and providing constructive feedback to foster growth.

Section 2: The EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors

This section presents the EELISA OS Ambassadors selected by the EELISA InnoCORE partners and elaborates on their collective efforts to implement Open Science initiatives. It details a collaborative work plan developed by the OS Ambassadors, categorizing tasks and associated actions aimed at effective communication, outreach, and sustainability activities. The goal is to establish a robust network of influential OS Ambassadors who will drive Open Science initiatives forward and nurture a culture of transparency and collaboration across all campuses within the EELISA network. This section also emphasizes the importance of continuous engagement and the dissemination of Open Science practices to ensure the long-term success and impact of the program.

- **Chapter 7: The Process of creating the OS Network of Ambassadors** introduces the ambassadors selected by the EELISA InnoCORE partners.
- **Chapter 8: Work Plan for Implementing Outreach Actions** discusses the work plan developed collaboratively by the OS ambassadors, categorizing tasks and associated actions.
- **Chapter 9: Dissemination and Sustainability Activities** summarizes the communication actions and potential connections to EELISA 2.0 to boost the OS Network of Ambassadors' sustainability.
- **Chapter 10: Concluding Remarks** wraps up the guide by summarizing key themes and offering further guidance for universities aiming to optimize their OS Ambassador programs and enhance the network across the alliance.

By adopting the strategies laid out in the OS Ambassador Blueprint and leveraging the collaborative efforts of the EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors, the consortium aims to cultivate a thriving Open Science environment across its institutions, enhancing the overall impact of scientific research and innovation.

**SECTION 1. The OS
Ambassador Blueprint: A
Guide to Effective
Recruitment and Active
Engagement**

1. Identifying Potential OS Ambassadors

The journey towards establishing an effective OS Ambassador Network starts with identifying the right individuals - those passionate about fostering transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in scientific research. The potential OS Ambassadors can emanate from a myriad of backgrounds, be it researchers, students, or administrative staff. These individuals are not merely defined by their roles, but by their dedication to propel an Open Science culture within the university campus.

Several universities across Europe have pioneered in this realm, successfully implementing OS Ambassador programs. Drawing upon their experiences and insights provides us a roadmap to identify and select potential ambassadors who can truly make a difference.

A Commitment to Open Science

The first attribute to look for in potential OS Ambassadors is an unwavering **commitment to Open Science principles**. Look for the marks they have left in their respective domains. Are there researchers who have been persistent in publishing in open-access journals or maintaining transparency in their data? Are there students who are active in citizen science projects, or administrative staff who champion for transparency and accessibility in university operations? These are the individuals who don't just preach Open Science, but practice it.

CASE IN POINT: University of Groningen

Consider the University of Groningen in the Netherlands. They have achieved great strides in their [OS Ambassador](#) program by prioritizing individuals who have shown consistent devotion to Open Science in their work, whether it be research or administrative tasks. This kind of commitment is often a strong indicator of their passion for Open Science, ensuring that their ambassadorial role is not just a title, but a natural extension of their own values and practices

Leadership Potential and Ability to Inspire Others

Beyond commitment, the potential OS Ambassadors should also embody strong **leadership traits**. They should be able to captivate, motivate, and inspire others to embrace Open Science. This requires charismatic speakers, influencers in their fields, or simply individuals known for their commitment and enthusiasm for Open Science. Look for those who have a natural ability to inspire and motivate those around them.

CASE IN POINT: University of Cambridge

The [University of Cambridge](#) in the UK offers an insightful example in this regard. They have found success by focusing on individuals who are well-respected within their respective departments. These individuals often hold sway in their academic circles and are therefore uniquely positioned to promote Open Science principles among their peers. They also often have the capacity to influence policy and practice, making them effective ambassadors for change.

Expertise

In addition to the attributes mentioned above, OS ambassadors should have a high level of expertise in their respective fields. This helps ensure they understand the intricacies of their domain and can effectively promote open science principles within it. Deep knowledge in a

specific field can also enable ambassadors to identify opportunities and challenges unique to their domain and adapt open science practices accordingly.

CASE IN POINT: ENLIGHT Open Science Ambassador Network

The [ENLIGHT Open Science Ambassador Network](#) is a collective of researchers associated with any of the ENLIGHT universities, who are actively involved in Open Science. These Ambassadors, who are passionate advocates of Open Science principles and methods, act as intermediaries between their university's research community and the ENLIGHT consortium.

Diversity: A Key Ingredient

Diversity is a vital component of any successful OS Ambassador program. It is paramount to ensure that the team of ambassadors represents a wide range of perspectives and experiences. This includes academic disciplines, career stages, cultural backgrounds, and more. Diversity enhances the richness of ideas, ensuring a comprehensive approach to promoting Open Science.

CASE IN POINT: Karolinska Institutet

An example comes from Sweden's [Karolinska Institute](#). They have purposefully incorporated diversity into their OS Ambassador program, resulting in a team of ambassadors that represent a wide range of research fields and ensures gender balance.

Process of Identification

After setting the attributes for ideal candidates for the ambassador role, the next task is - how do we discover these people? The key is in **effective communication**. It's crucial to spread the mission and core values of Open Science across the university extensively. Plan and execute various activities like **seminars, workshops, and open discussions**. Engage both students and faculty members in discussions revolving around Open Science. These initiatives will naturally attract those with a fervor for Open Science. Furthermore, these discussions and events can also be elevated to a collaborative level by organizing **joint events** at the EELISA level.

Moreover, collaborate with department heads, research advisors, and student leaders to identify potential candidates. They can provide insights about individuals who have demonstrated a commitment to Open Science, shown leadership potential, and contributed to the diversity of thought.

Consider conducting an **open call** for OS Ambassadors. An open call allows for individuals who are interested to come forward, which may identify passionate individuals that might have otherwise been overlooked.

Identifying potential OS Ambassadors is a process that requires careful consideration and thoughtful approach. It is about finding those individuals who are deeply committed to Open Science, who have the ability to lead and inspire others, and who bring diverse perspectives. By learning from the experiences of successful OS Ambassador programs across Europe, universities can refine their identification process to build a team of effective ambassadors.

CASE IN POINT: LERU Open Science Ambassadors

In 2019, an Ad Hoc Group on Open Science (AHG on OS) was established to implement the LERU Open Science Roadmap, culminating in the 'Implementing Open Science' report. In 2020, the AHG on OS transitioned responsibilities to the LERU Ad Hoc Group

['Open Science Ambassadors'](#) (AHG OSA), shifting the implementation focus to local institutions.

The primary role of an Open Science Ambassador at a LERU university involves providing leadership in executing the report's recommendations across the European Commission's eight pillars of Open Science. As advocates for Open Science, the ambassadors also serve as trusted advisors, addressing the concerns of the university community, acknowledging disciplinary differences, and promoting flexibility.

The AHG OSA, which includes ambassadors from LERU institutions, operates as a hub for assessing progress, sharing ideas, identifying best practices, and collaborating on potential strategies. It also tackles emerging themes, with ambassador subgroups working alongside LERU policy groups during new policy development.

In the next chapters, we will dive deeper into the recruitment process, defining roles and responsibilities, providing effective training and support, and strategizing for active engagement. Each step, carefully designed and implemented, takes us closer to our goal - fostering a thriving Open Science culture within the university campus.

2. The Recruitment Process

The recruitment process of OS Ambassadors is a critical step in fostering an environment that champions transparency, collaboration, and accessibility in scientific research. As we learned from the previous chapter, identifying potential candidates is the first step. We now explore the strategies that will transform potential candidates into active, effective Open Science Ambassadors.

Universities of science and technology across the globe, given their heavy reliance on research, have been at the forefront of implementing innovative recruitment strategies. As we explore this process, we will draw from their experiences to elucidate the various elements involved.

Setting Clear Expectations

The first step in the recruitment process is clearly defining what being an Open Science Ambassador entails. Potential candidates must understand their roles and responsibilities, the level of commitment required, and the expected outcomes of their ambassadorship.

CASE IN POINT: Arqus European University Alliance

The Arqus European University Alliance offers an example in this respect. They have recruited [OS Ambassadors](#). The Arqus Open Science Ambassador program was seeking passionate and experienced Open Science ambassadors to promote Open Science principles across the Arqus alliance universities and beyond. Ambassadors are expected to:

- Inspire and engage researchers, especially PhD students and postdocs, to practice Open Science.
- Communicate needs and expectations regarding Open Science from a researcher's perspective to Arqus members.
- Support others with their expertise, particularly in the development of Open Science training materials and advising

researchers aiming to incorporate more openness into their research processes.

Qualifications for ambassadors include a strong motivation to promote Open Science, significant experience in one or more Open Science fields, and basic knowledge of Open Science networks and infrastructures.

Inviting Applications

After setting clear expectations, the next step is to invite applications. There are several ways to do this, ranging from an **open call to nominations** or **direct appointments**. A combination of these methods can be an effective approach, as it allows the recruitment process to be both inclusive and targeted.

Evaluation and Selection

Once applications have been received, the next step is to evaluate candidates and select the ambassadors. Evaluation criteria will typically include the candidates' commitment to Open Science, leadership potential, ability to inspire others, and their contribution to the diversity of the ambassador team.

Appointment Period and Network Enrichment

Partner universities should decide the period of appointment for the Open Science Ambassadors. It is crucial that while determining this period, they take into consideration the need to enrich the network of ambassadors continually. Ensuring a dynamic and diverse network is essential for fostering a robust Open Science community, facilitating knowledge exchange, and enhancing the overall impact of Open Science initiatives across institutions.

Providing a Platform for Engagement

Following the selection process, newly appointed ambassadors should be formally introduced to the university community. This introduction serves two purposes. First, it provides recognition to the ambassadors, boosting their morale and commitment. Second, it ensures that the rest of the community is aware of their roles and can reach out to them for guidance and support regarding Open Science.

CASE IN POINT: Open Science Communities of Practice across Europe

[OSC-NL](#) is a flourishing and expanding grassroots initiative, driven by community leadership, forming a robust social structure of Open Science Communities across the Netherlands. Comprising over 2000 researchers, the Dutch OSC network is primed to implement Open Science principles. Furthermore, OSC-NL contributes to policy and service development, reflecting the desires and requirements of their community members, and thus actively influencing the transition to Open Science based on researchers' experiences.

[Open Science Community Utrecht](#) (OSCU) was initiated to expedite the adoption of Open Science practices, particularly targeting those new to the field. Its objectives include: (1) fostering the exchange of Open Science practices among colleagues, (2) motivating and assisting researchers to take their initial or subsequent modest steps into the realm of Open Science, (3) contributing to Open Science policies, infrastructures, and support services, thereby moulding the transition to Open Science, and (4) investigating and encouraging collaborations

between academics and societal stakeholders for mutual inspiration and co-creation.

Recruiting Open Science Ambassadors is a careful, meticulous process, but with a structured approach, it can result in a team of passionate individuals ready to advocate for open science principles. By setting clear expectations, inviting applications, selecting the right candidates, and properly introducing them to the university community, universities can ensure the success of their OS Ambassador programs. In the next chapter, we will explore the roles and responsibilities of an OS Ambassador in greater detail, drawing on the practices of various universities to provide a comprehensive overview.

3. Roles and Responsibilities of an OS Ambassador

Open Science Ambassadors (OSAs) play a vital role in promoting the principles of open science within their institutions. Their roles and responsibilities vary but center around advocacy, education, and support. This chapter delves into these roles, discussing the expectations and responsibilities of an OS Ambassador.

Advocacy

One of the primary roles of an OS Ambassador is advocacy. OSAs are champions of open science within their institutions. They promote open science principles and practices among their peers and superiors, advocating for institutional policies that support open science.

Advocacy often involves speaking at meetings and events, serving on relevant committees, and engaging in discussions about research practices and policies. Ambassadors may also be tasked with engaging external stakeholders, such as funders and policymakers, to promote open science.

Table 1. Responsibilities associated with the advocacy role

Roles	Responsibilities	Description
Advocacy	Promoting Open Science Principles and Practices	Advocacy begins with promoting the principles and practices of Open Science among peers and superiors. This promotion may take the form of personal interactions, formal presentations, or casual discussions during gatherings and events. OS Ambassadors emphasize the benefits of Open Science, such as enhanced transparency, increased reproducibility of results, broader collaboration, and greater public trust in research. The ambassador might showcase successful examples of Open Science within their institutions, demonstrating its real-world impacts, or bring to attention the latest trends, research, and tools in the Open Science landscape.

Roles	Responsibilities	Description
	Influencing Institutional Policies	<p>Another important aspect of advocacy is contributing to the development and refinement of institutional policies to support Open Science. This might involve working with university leadership, research offices, libraries, or IT departments. Ambassadors can provide valuable input into creating conducive policies or modifying existing ones to better align with Open Science principles.</p> <p>OS Ambassadors can work towards institutional endorsement of the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), push for infrastructural changes that enable the adoption of Open Science practices, or advocate for incentives and recognition for researchers who adopt Open Science principles.</p>
	Engagement with External Stakeholders	<p>Advocacy is not limited to the institution's confines. OS Ambassadors might also engage with external stakeholders to promote Open Science. This can include dialogues with funding bodies to encourage Open Science-friendly funding policies, such as mandates for open access publication or data sharing.</p> <p>They might also interact with policymakers to influence Open Science-friendly regulations and standards at the regional, national, or even international level. Such activities broaden the reach of Open Science, encouraging its adoption on a larger scale.</p>
	Advocacy Through Personal Practice	<p>Last but not least, OS Ambassadors advocate for Open Science by embodying its principles in their own research practices. By openly sharing their research outputs, using Open Science tools, and collaborating openly, they can serve as role models within their community. Their personal practices can provide tangible demonstrations of Open Science in action, inspiring others to follow suit.</p>

The advocacy role of Open Science Ambassadors is complex and multifaceted, involving a blend of promotion, policy influence, stakeholder engagement, and personal practice. Successful advocacy can significantly accelerate the adoption of Open Science within an institution and beyond, making it a critical aspect of an Ambassador's duties.

Education

OS Ambassadors also have a vital role in educating their colleagues about open science. This involves informing peers about the benefits of open science, such as increased reproducibility, transparency, and public trust in science. It also includes training peers in open science practices.

Education can take many forms, from informal conversations to formal training sessions or workshops. It could also involve curating resources on open science, such as guides, toolkits, and online courses. Given the rapidly evolving nature of open science, OS Ambassadors often have to stay updated with the latest developments in the field, attending relevant training themselves.

Table 2. Responsibilities associated with the education role

Roles	Responsibilities	Description
Education	Disseminating the Philosophy and Benefits of Open Science	<p>First and foremost, the educational role of an Open Science Ambassador involves informing colleagues about the philosophy and ethos of open science. This involves clarifying the principle that knowledge should be open and accessible to all and explaining the tangible benefits that can stem from such a philosophy.</p> <p>Increased reproducibility, transparency, and public trust are key benefits of open science that the ambassador needs to communicate. They need to explain how open science can foster a more collaborative and inclusive research environment, increase the speed of scientific discovery, and ensure that the outputs of research are more readily available to those who can benefit from them.</p>
	Training Peers in Open Science Practices	<p>Aside from disseminating the philosophy of open science, ambassadors are also responsible for training their peers in the practical aspects of open science. They need to familiarize their colleagues with the tools and practices that can make science more open, including preprints, open data, open code, open access publications, and the use of open licenses.</p> <p>Training can take the form of formal workshops or seminars, as well as more informal one-on-one sessions or group discussions. The training sessions should be designed to cater to varying levels of familiarity with open science, ensuring that everyone from novices to experienced researchers can benefit.</p>
	Curating Resources on Open Science	<p>Another important educational responsibility of an Open Science Ambassador is to curate resources on open science. These resources could include guides, toolkits, online courses, or lists of relevant literature. By creating and maintaining a repository of open science resources, ambassadors can provide their colleagues with the tools they need to learn about and implement open science practices.</p>
	Staying Updated and Self-education	<p>Finally, given the rapidly evolving nature of open science, ambassadors are tasked with staying updated with the latest trends, developments, and debates in the field. This could involve attending conferences, webinars, or training sessions, reading relevant literature, or participating in online forums and discussions. Staying updated is essential for the ambassador to provide the most current and relevant advice to their colleagues.</p>

The educational role of an Open Science Ambassador is multifaceted and essential. By disseminating the philosophy of open science, training peers in open science practices, curating resources, and staying updated with the latest developments, ambassadors can drive the adoption of open science in their institutions and make a lasting impact on their colleagues' research practices.

Support

Ambassadors provide support to researchers in their open science practices. This could involve assisting colleagues with making their research openly available, whether it's data, code, or publications. They could provide advice on using open science tools, complying with open access policies, or applying for open science badges.

Support could also involve mediating between researchers and other stakeholders in the institution, such as the library or the IT department. Ambassadors can help address technical or logistical barriers to open science, advocating for the necessary resources and infrastructure.

Table 3. Responsibilities associated with the support role

Roles	Responsibilities	Description
Support	Assisting with Open Science Practices	<p>Open Science Ambassadors (OSAs) play a vital role in providing practical support to researchers in their open science endeavors. The breadth and depth of Open Science can sometimes be overwhelming, especially for researchers who are new to it. OSAs step in to guide and assist their colleagues in making their research more open.</p> <p>This might involve helping researchers navigate the process of making their research outputs - such as data, code, or publications - openly available. OSAs could provide guidance on selecting appropriate repositories, understanding and applying open licenses, and using specific Open Science tools or platforms.</p> <p>Moreover, they can offer advice on complying with open access policies of different journals, research funders, or the institution itself. This could include interpreting policy language, suggesting strategies to meet policy requirements, or assisting with the process of applying for waivers or exemptions if necessary.</p> <p>OSAs might also support researchers in applying for open science badges, which are a form of recognition for researchers who adopt open practices. They can help understand the criteria for different badges, assist in compiling the necessary evidence, and guide through the application process.</p>

Roles	Responsibilities	Description
	Mediating Between Researchers and Other Stakeholders	<p>Open Science Ambassadors also serve as a bridge between researchers and other stakeholders in the institution involved in the Open Science process. These stakeholders could include the library, the IT department, research support services, or the institution's leadership.</p> <p>For example, if a researcher is encountering technical difficulties in using an Open Science tool or platform, the OSA could liaise with the IT department to resolve the issue. If a researcher is unsure about the appropriate repository for their data, the OSA could consult with the library or research support services to provide the necessary guidance.</p> <p>In cases where institutional policies or infrastructure are hindering the adoption of Open Science, OSAs can advocate on behalf of the researchers. They can communicate the challenges and needs to the institution's leadership and work towards obtaining the necessary resources and infrastructure.</p>

The supporting role of an Open Science Ambassador is multifaceted and essential. By providing practical assistance, advice, and serving as a liaison between researchers and other stakeholders, OSAs play a significant role in overcoming barriers to Open Science. Their support not only eases the implementation of Open Science practices but also fosters a more supportive and conducive environment for Open Science in their institutions.

Community Building

In addition to these roles, OS Ambassadors often have a role in building a community around open science within their institutions. They can help organize events, such as open science fairs or hackathons, that bring together researchers interested in open science.

Building a community can also involve online activities, such as managing a mailing list or a chat group on open science. This community-building role contributes to a culture change towards open science, fostering an environment that values and rewards open science practices.

CASE IN POINT: *Open Science Community Delft*

The [Open Science Community Delft](#) operates as a learning community where members aid each other in improving their open, collaborative, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) practices. They achieve this by sharing their expertise and taking part in various educational opportunities. The community provides the environment and resources needed for its members to initiate their own open projects. It is a dynamically evolving and learning entity, effectively a perpetual "work-in-progress", always open to new insights and suggestions. The Open Science Community Delft serves as a repository of information, a host of events, and a wellspring of stories.

Table 4. Responsibilities associated with the community building role

Roles	Responsibilities	Description
Community building	Organizing Open Science Events	<p>One of the most effective ways of building a community is through organizing events centered around open science. Open Science Ambassadors could spearhead or facilitate the organization of open science fairs, hackathons, seminars, workshops, or roundtable discussions. These events bring together researchers, students, and staff interested in open science, promoting knowledge sharing, collaboration, and the development of new ideas.</p> <p>For instance, an open science fair could showcase open science projects from different disciplines, while a hackathon could challenge participants to create new open science tools or solutions. Seminars or workshops could provide platforms for discussing open science trends, sharing success stories, or collectively addressing challenges.</p>
	Cultivating Online Open Science Communities	<p>In today's digital age, community building is not limited to physical interactions. Open Science Ambassadors can foster online communities, utilizing digital platforms to bring together those interested in open science.</p> <p>For instance, they could manage a mailing list, sharing regular updates on open science news, resources, events, and opportunities. They could also create and moderate a chat group or an online forum, providing a space for continuous discussion, inquiry, and collaboration on open science.</p> <p>These online communities can cater to diverse needs – for example, some members might be seeking advice on open science practices, others might want to share their open science experiences, while others might be looking for collaboration opportunities. A vibrant online community can foster a sense of belonging, engagement, and collective learning among its members.</p>
	Shaping Open Science Culture	<p>The community-building role of Open Science Ambassadors significantly contributes to culture change towards open science within institutions. By fostering an environment that values, practices, and rewards open science, they are gradually shaping a culture that views openness as the norm rather than the exception.</p>

The roles and responsibilities of Open Science Ambassadors are indeed manifold and challenging but equally rewarding. Through their contribution, ambassadors can significantly advance open science, shaping research practices to be more transparent, reliable, and inclusive.

However, it's essential to acknowledge that while this chapter has outlined some common roles and responsibilities, the specifics can and do vary across institutions. Understanding the context of each institution is crucial in shaping the Ambassador's role and determining the most effective strategies for promoting open science. The next chapter will discuss how to provide effective training and support to OS Ambassadors, ensuring they are equipped to fulfill their diverse roles.

4. Effective Training and Support for OS Ambassadors

For Open Science Ambassadors to be effective in their roles, they require robust training and enduring support mechanisms. This section delves into the multi-faceted strategies to ensure ambassadors are thoroughly equipped with the requisite knowledge, skills, and resources, and receive sustained support throughout their tenure.

Figure 1. Dimensions of OS Ambassadors training and support

Initial Induction: Open Science Principles and Best Practices

The cornerstone of preparing OS Ambassadors lies in conducting comprehensive initial induction sessions. These sessions should offer an in-depth understanding of the ethos of open science, its varied methodologies, and global best practices, along with the specific guidelines laid down by the university. A blend of theoretical teachings and hands-on exercises would ensure all-round proficiency. This foundational training could be effectively delivered through various channels such as online modules, workshops, seminars, and webinars.

Continuous Learning Opportunities

Given the dynamic nature of Open Science, it's pivotal for ambassadors to stay abreast of the latest advancements and shifts in the field. Facilitating perpetual learning opportunities like advanced-level workshops, lectures from renowned open science experts, and access to e-learning courses and resources would keep ambassadors at the forefront of open science trends. Regular updates on changes to open science policy, novel tools, and practices are essential.

CASE IN POINT: *Open Science Community Delft*

This [catalog](#) encompasses events, curated by members of the Open Science Community Delft, which could be of relevance to other associates. Should any member desire to enrich this list with an

additional event, they are respectfully encouraged to submit their proposition through an issue on GitHub. By adhering to a co-design approach, the community welcomes proposals for other events from university community members, thus promoting active engagement and growth within the Open Science community.

Implementation of a Mentorship or Peer-Support Program

Fostering a supportive network can be instrumental in aiding ambassadors to effectively manage the challenges and responsibilities of their role. Implementing a **mentorship or peer-support scheme** can promote knowledge sharing, offer emotional support, and encourage collaborative problem-solving. **Experienced ambassadors** or university staff with expertise in open science could serve as mentors, providing invaluable advice and guidance to new or less-experienced ambassadors.

Provision of Essential Resources, Tools, and Platforms

OS Ambassadors must have access to pertinent tools and resources to promote and implement open science effectively. This could include open science toolkits, instructional guides, databases, or platforms dedicated to sharing open data or research outputs. A curated list of these resources or a dedicated portal, such as an 'OS Training Hub,' can significantly assist ambassadors in their tasks.

Institutional Support and Recognition

Last but not least, acknowledging the importance of institutional support is essential. Recognition of the hard work and achievements of ambassadors can significantly enhance their morale and motivation. Regular interactions can help identify any issues they may be facing and provide timely support and guidance.

In conclusion, comprehensive training and sustained support are critical to empowering OS Ambassadors with the skills, knowledge, and resources they need to promote open science successfully. By dedicating efforts to these aspects, universities can ensure the durability and effectiveness of their OS Ambassador programs, further enhancing the goal and influence of open science.

5. Strategies for Active Engagement

The efficacy of any Open Science Ambassador network leans heavily not just on the selection of appropriate ambassadors or their clear roles and responsibilities, but also on how actively engaged these ambassadors are in spreading the principles of open science throughout the university. This chapter focuses on various strategies (see Figure 2) to cultivate such active engagement, encompassing hosting regular events, developing individualized outreach plans, and fostering collaboration among university stakeholders.

Figure 2. Recommended strategies for OSA engagement

Creating a Regular Events Calendar

Frequent engagement in a variety of events is a tried and tested method of keeping OSAs actively involved. Regular open science events provide a platform for OSAs to discuss, learn, and network. They can partake in open forums to exchange ideas, workshops to learn and teach new open science techniques, or lectures that broaden their understanding of open science.

Involving OSAs in the organization and execution of these events can keep them actively engaged. By taking ownership, ambassadors will likely become more invested in the initiative and their roles, and the firsthand experience they gain in planning and coordinating will be invaluable.

Developing Individualized Outreach Plans

A tailored outreach plan specific to each ambassador can also help boost engagement. Open Science Ambassadors come from a variety of departments or research areas, each with its unique dynamics. An outreach plan customized to fit the ambassador's specific environment will ensure they remain actively engaged and their work has the most impact.

OSAs can start by assessing the needs within their departments or research areas. Following this, they can design an outreach plan that uses suitable methods of communication and engagement, while also considering their own strengths and limitations. The creation of these plans empowers ambassadors, providing them with a sense of ownership and autonomy that can be a potent motivator for active engagement.

Fostering Collaboration among University Stakeholders

Another critical strategy for active engagement involves fostering collaborations within the university. Partnering with other university stakeholders such as librarians, research support services, and senior leadership can help OSAs feel part of a larger initiative, increasing their motivation and engagement.

For instance, collaboration with librarians, who often possess knowledge in information management and access, can provide OSAs with additional insight into open science. Working with research support services can align the OSA program with the university's broader research

strategy. Engaging with the senior leadership of the university can bring about an institutional acceptance and promotion of open science, further motivating OSAs.

Exchange Programs within EELISA

Exchange programs within EELISA can be an innovative and compelling way to keep OS Ambassadors actively engaged. These programs offer OSAs an opportunity to learn from their peers at other institutions, share best practices, and bring new ideas back to their home universities.

Participation in an exchange program can invigorate the ambassadors by exposing them to different perspectives and experiences. This exposure can provide fresh ideas and new ways of promoting open science, thus enhancing the ambassadors' efforts at their own institutions. The cultural exchange that these programs foster also contributes to the diversity and inclusivity goals of the Open Science movement.

This strategy, in combination with regular events, tailored outreach plans, collaborations, and mentorship programs, creates a comprehensive approach to maintaining the active engagement of Open Science Ambassadors.

The active engagement of Open Science Ambassadors is central to the success of the OSA Network.

As we proceed, it's crucial to remember that active engagement isn't a one-time effort but an ongoing process. It requires dedication, flexibility, and a passion for open science. By actively engaging OSAs, universities can cultivate a culture that values transparency, inclusivity, and collaboration, contributing to the advancement of science and society as a whole.

CASE IN POINT: SEA-EU Open Science Staff Week

The reSEArch-Eu project of the European Seas Alliance (SEA EU) conducted the "[Open Science Staff Week](#)" (OSSW) in Cádiz, co-organized by the University of Malta. The focus was on advancing a common Open Science data management policy. The reSEArch-UE project's key goals involve connecting scientific data repositories among consortium universities and fostering an open science culture via training activities.

6. Evaluation and Feedback

Evaluating the work of Open Science Ambassadors is essential for the ongoing refinement, growth, and improvement of the program. This assessment should be aligned with institutional policies, the specific context, and the profile of each ambassador. Deliverable [D3.2 The OS Strategic Planning and Implementation Guide](#) comprises descriptors and indicators that could be used by partner institutions in the process of defining evaluation criteria for the OS ambassadors. By adopting a systematic approach to evaluation and feedback, the program can accurately measure the effectiveness of each ambassador's efforts, identify areas for improvement, and provide ambassadors with the necessary support and guidance to excel in their roles. This chapter provides insights to assist institutions in outlining the critical components of an effective evaluation and feedback mechanism for Open Science Ambassadors.

Figure 3. Components of the Evaluation and Feedback Mechanism

Objective Evaluation Criteria

Evaluation starts by establishing clear, objective criteria. These criteria should be fair, transparent, and tied to the core objectives of the OSA network. Performance metrics could include the number of open science workshops or events conducted by the ambassador, the number of researchers or students reached, or specific project outcomes tied to the promotion of open science within the institution.

The criteria could also include softer measures, such as an ambassador's ability to foster collaborations within the university, their engagement in mentorship programs, or their contributions to the community-building activities. The inclusion of both quantitative and qualitative metrics ensures a balanced and comprehensive evaluation of the ambassadors' performance.

Regular Reviews and Feedback

Once the evaluation criteria are established, it's vital to conduct regular reviews. These reviews should incorporate feedback not just from the ambassadors themselves but also from the wider university community, including researchers, students, and other stakeholders the ambassadors interact with.

Self-evaluations can provide insights into an ambassador's perspective on their performance, any challenges they have faced, and their suggestions for improvement. Peer feedback from other OS Ambassadors can also be invaluable, offering a view from individuals who understand the intricacies of the role. Feedback from the wider community can provide an external perspective on the impact of the ambassador's work.

Enriching the Network

The primary goal of evaluation and feedback should be to enrich and strengthen the OSA network. Feedback should be viewed as a valuable resource for identifying both common challenges and best practices within the network.

For example, if feedback reveals that ambassadors in particular areas feel isolated or are struggling with specific issues, steps can be taken to strengthen connections between these ambassadors and others within the network. This could be achieved through regular virtual meetings, mentorship programs, or the development of collaborative projects.

Additionally, if feedback highlights that certain ambassadors have developed effective strategies for promoting open science within their institution, these insights can be shared across the network. By fostering this kind of knowledge exchange, the network can ensure that all ambassadors benefit from the experiences and successes of their peers.

It is also crucial to consider how the network itself can be expanded and diversified, given the fact that it is a living body. Feedback can help identify gaps in representation or areas where the network could be strengthened. This could lead to targeted recruitment efforts or collaborations with other networks or organizations.

Feedback should not only be used to identify areas of improvement but also to recognize and celebrate the successes of the ambassadors and the network as a whole. Regular recognition of achievements can boost morale, foster a sense of community, and encourage ambassadors to continue their efforts in promoting open science.

In conclusion, regular evaluation and feedback play a pivotal role in enriching the OSA network. They provide the insights needed to foster stronger connections between ambassadors, promote knowledge exchange, and continually expand and diversify the network. This process is not a one-off task but a recurring cycle that encourages a culture of continual learning, improvement, and excellence within the OSA network.

SECTION 2. The EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors

7. The Process of creating the OS Network of Ambassadors

Timeline and milestones

Figure 4 outlines the key milestones and activities in the development of the OS Network of Ambassadors. Starting with the launch of the D3.2 Open Science Strategic Planning and Implementation Guide in August 2022, this timeline highlights the critical steps taken to establish and activate the network, culminating in the formal establishment and the commencement of dissemination activities.

Figure 4. Evolution of the OS Network of Ambassadors

In August 2022, the **D3.2 Open Science Strategic Planning and Implementation Guide** was launched, initiating a unified approach for EELISA InnoCORE partners to re-evaluate their strategic planning and implementation of Open Science. The document presented recommendations for mutual activities, including the establishment of the OS Network of Ambassadors. Following these recommendations, the focus shifted to implementing the OS process at local universities through the development of Open Science Action Plans (OSAPs) by each university partners as provided in **D3.3. deliverable 'Updated OS Institutional policies and Implementation/Action Plans'**.

Given that Open Science Ambassadors play a crucial role in supporting researchers with their open science initiatives, they will directly and indirectly contribute to the implementation of various practices outlined in the Open Science Action Plans (OSAPs) at the institutional level, while the responsibility for implementing the OSAPs stays with the universities.

To support this implementation, the guide recommended that each university appoint an Open Science Ambassador and establish the Group of OS Ambassadors at the EELISA level. The EELISA Open Science Community (OSC) was indicated to play a crucial role in nominating and facilitating cooperation among OS ambassadors. The [EELISA communities](#) are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

Each community will define its main elements: mission, challenges, people/organization, activities, and evaluation criteria. Initiated in September 2022, the EELISA Open Science Community adopts a bottom-up approach to drive cultural change towards openness. Recognizing the necessity of this transition, the members aim to support the transformation within the alliance and member institutions by staying aligned with global developments and leveraging the competencies of EELISA. The goal is to enhance research, education, and innovation through open science practices, thereby increasing efficiency and productivity in accordance with the EU's open science policy. By bringing together and collaborating with all beneficiaries, stakeholders, and experts, the community strives to ensure that society benefits maximally from science through the policies, strategies, and tools developed by EELISA as part of the open science ecosystem.

The OS Community has an online presence as well [Link to the page](#)

These ambassadors, forming the Group of OS Ambassadors, were envisioned as facilitators, representatives, and voices for Open Science at their respective institutions. Their roles included applying OS recommendations, raising awareness, sharing information, and organizing events. Thus, D3.2 stated that it was essential for each university to nominate the most suitable person for this role.

The focus shifted to the local implementation of the Open Science process. During the **OS Forum in Bucharest**, held in [March 2023](#), discussions were held about the initial profile of OS Ambassadors. The forum emphasized the importance of selecting suitable individuals who could effectively lead Open Science initiatives and foster collaboration among EELISA universities. Building on the takeaways from the Forum, the University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest started to document and draft a document to support the partners in the process of recruiting and selecting the OS ambassadors.

In July 2023, the blueprint for the OS Ambassadors, **D3.6 The OS Ambassador Blueprint: A Guide to Effective Recruitment and Active Engagement**, was launched during the EELISA InnoCORE meeting in Istanbul. The OS Ambassador Blueprint was crafted to assist EELISA InnoCORE universities in effectively identifying, recruiting, training, and engaging Open Science Ambassadors.

Following the guidelines, the partners initiated the selection process and completed it by September 2023. In the same month, the online page for the OS Network was launched, thus achieving milestone **MS3: Launch of the Network of OS Ambassadors**. This milestone marked the formal establishment of the OS Ambassadors Network, which aims to ensure consistent and effective dissemination of Open Science practices.

[Visit the OS Network of Ambassadors' page](#)

The Network of Open Science Ambassadors commenced its activities by reviewing ongoing actions, exchanging ideas, identifying best practices, and addressing new topics that required updated policies. This collaborative effort was essential for developing new strategies and action plans.

October 2023 saw the commencement of dissemination activities, with the launch of the **OS Network of Ambassadors on social media**. This initiative was crucial for spreading awareness and engaging a broader audience in the Open Science dialogue.

In November 2023, the OS Ambassadors were provided with a template to design **outreach plans**. All the plans were collected by the UPB team (see Section 8). Following this, the ambassadors began the implementation of these plans by continuing existing activities and

initiating new ones. They organized workshops, seminars, and collaborative projects to foster a deeper understanding and application of Open Science practices within their universities.

Throughout this process, the Open Science Ambassadors facilitated the adoption of Open Science practices, ensuring that EELISA universities became exemplary models in the international landscape of Open Science. Their efforts were instrumental in driving forward the Open Science agenda, enhancing collaboration, and promoting a culture of openness and transparency in research.

Presentation of the EELISA Network of OS Ambassadors

Following an internal selection process, the Open Science Ambassadors have been appointed (see Table 5), and the network is now fully functional. Each ambassador has been formally recognized both within their individual institutions and throughout the EELISA community. As advocates for transformative change, these OS Ambassadors will play a crucial role in promoting an environment of open, collaborative, and reproducible research across the campus, aiding EELISA in advancing these progressive scientific practices.

The EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors comprises a diverse group of individuals selected from various professional backgrounds within the academic and research communities. This diversity reflects the multifaceted nature of Open Science and the need for broad representation to effectively promote and implement its principles. Below is an analysis of the types of profiles selected as ambassadors.

Figure 5 illustrates the gender distribution of the OS Ambassadors within the EELISA network. The analysis reveals that there are six male ambassadors and three female ambassadors. While this distribution shows a greater number of male ambassadors, it still highlights the EELISA network's efforts to include both genders in the promotion and implementation of Open Science practices.

Figure 5. The gender distribution of the OS Ambassadors

The network includes dedicated librarians like **Burcu Bulut** from Istanbul Technical University (ITU), who holds a Ph.D. in Information and Records Management and has been actively involved in various open access initiatives. **Markus Putnings** from the University Library Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU) serves as the Head of Open Access, overseeing numerous aspects of Open Access and research data management. Similarly, **Sylvie Fayet** from PSL heads the department for libraries cooperation and Open Science, drawing on her extensive experience in cultural heritage management and IT applications in librarianship.

Among the professors and researchers, **Stefano Palagi** from SSSA is an Associate Professor and a member of the Open Science Commission, with a background in Biomedical

Engineering and Biorobotics. **Ciprian Dobre** from the National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest (UNSTPB) is a Professor of Computer Science and Vice-Rector, recognized for his significant contributions to data science, mobile computing, and Open Science. **Óscar Corcho**, a Full Professor at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), co-leads the Ontology Engineering Group and focuses on the Semantic Web, Linked Data, and Open Science. **Lorenzo Bartalesi**, an Associate Professor at Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS), is a leader in international relations with a keen interest in Open Science and active involvement in European research initiatives.

Administrative staff also play a crucial role in the network. **Cecilia Liskay** from Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME) is a ranking manager with a background in open-access editorial systems, responsible for submitting data to ranking agencies. **Romain Boistel** from the École des Ponts (ENPC) works in the Scholarly Communication Department, managing electronic resources and promoting Open Science among researchers.

Table 5. The EELISA Network of OS Ambassadors

Burcu Bulut, ITU

Librarian at Istanbul Technical University

Burcu Bulut received her Ph.D. degree from Ankara University, Department of Information and Records Management in 2011 and she joined Istanbul Technical University in 2019 as librarian and has played an active role in promoting open science as a group member of the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) Project (2011-2016) and Anadolu University Libraries Consortium Open Access and Institutional Repositories Working Group (2012-2016). She is currently a member of ITU EELISA innoCORE WP3 (EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science Practices) Team and co-coordinator of the EELISA Open Science Community. You can reach her here [linkedin.com/in/burcubulut/](https://www.linkedin.com/in/burcubulut/)

E-mail address: bulutburcu@itu.edu.tr

Markus Putnings, FAU

Head of Open Access at the University Library Erlangen-Nürnberg

Markus Putnings, originally trained as a bookseller, studied business informatics, worked in a publishing house, and completed a library traineeship for the higher library service. He became a senior librarian at Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU) and its university library in 2012, where he is responsible for all aspects of Open Access (OA). This includes concluding OA transformation agreements, advising researchers, managing the OA publication funds, providing information on quality aspects as well as scientometrics, predatory publishers, indexing & abstracting, and much more. In addition, he is the deputy head of research data management at FAU's university library, where he oversees all aspects of open data. He was involved in the creation of FAU's Open Science Policy and is committed to all aspects of openness. For example, thanks to his efforts, FAU's university library was awarded the Open Library Badge

(<https://badge.openbiblio.eu/>) in 2022. More information can be found at <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6014-9048>.

E-mail address: markus.putnings@fau.de

STEFANO PALAGI, SSSA

Associate Professor, member of the Open Science Commission

Stefano Palagi obtained a MSc degree in Biomedical Engineering in 2009 at the University of Pisa (Italy), and a PhD in Innovative Technologies – Biorobotics at the Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (Pisa, Italy) in January 2013. He then was a research fellow at Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, a postdoctoral researcher at the Max Planck Institute for Intelligent Systems (Stuttgart, Germany), and a postdoctoral researcher at Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia. In February 2021 he started as Assistant Professor at the BioRobotics Institute of the Sant'Anna School, where he currently is Associate Professor, PI of the Microscale Robotics Laboratory, and vice-coordinator of the PhD in BioRobotics. He is also part of the Gender Equality Plan working group and of the Open Science Commission of the Sant'Anna School.

E-mail address: stefano.palagi@santannapisa.it

Ciprian Dobre, UNSTPB

Professor of Computer Science, Vice-Rector at the National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest

Ciprian Dobre (Prof. dr. eng. with habilitation) (male), has scientific and scholarly contributions on Data Science, Mobile and Ubiquitous Computing, Internet of Things, Wireless Networks, Modeling / Simulation, Mobile and Urban Smart Technologies. Leading the MobyLab laboratory at UPB, he managed projects in fields like data engineering and Open Science, sensing&monitoring, intelligent traffic management and data collection and analytics for urban congestion and air pollution reduction and others. He was awarded the Award "Gheorghe Cartianu" of the Romanian Science Academy, for work on "Optimised communication using people-centric ad-hoc networks" (in 2016), and he was Fellow for California Institute of Technology for over 10 years. He was awarded an Oracle PhD fellowship during his doctoral studies. His results received one IBM Faculty Award, two CENIC Awards (for worldwide records in high-speed networking demonstrated at SuperComputing), and four Best Paper Awards. His results were published in over 100 books, chapters in edited books, articles in major international peer-reviewed journal, and well-established international conferences and workshops. He is the UPB representative as member in EOSC and member of CESAER (the forum of universities of science and technology in Europe), Scientific Evaluator for European

Commission and for national funding agencies in different programmes. He is a member of EUA Research and Innovation Strategy Group (RISG), the board developing the research and innovation strategy and policy for all topics of relevance to European HEIs, providing advice and support to the EUA Board on strategic horizon scanning and policy review. More information can be found at <https://crescdi.pub.ro/#!/profile/534>.

E-mail address: ciprian.dobre@upb.ro

Cecilia Liskay, BME

Ranking manager, BME Rector's Office Department of Research and Innovation

Cecilia Liskay has worked for nearly ten years as an editor of the open-access journals of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics and Eötvös Loránd University. She has gained expertise in open-source editorial systems (OJS) and databases. Since 2021, she has been a ranking manager at the Department of Research and Innovation. She is responsible for submitting data to ranking agencies such as THE and QS and analyzing the ranking results. As Secretary of the Scientific Council, she has gained insight into developing institutional strategies such as the Open Science and Open Access Strategy.

E-Mail address: Liskay.cecilia@bme.hu

Romain Boistel, ENPC

Librarian

Romain Boistel is working in the Scholarly Communication Department at the Library of the École des Ponts, a team of 3 people providing services to researchers. He is especially in charge of electronic resources subscriptions, open archive and open data repositories management (HAL and Recherche Data Gouv), and raising awareness and promoting Open Science among École des Ponts' researchers as part of the École des Ponts' Open Science Plan.

SYLVIE FAYET, PSL

Head of department for libraries cooperation and open science, PSL ambassador

Sylvie Fayet worked for various institutions (Ministry of Culture, national and academic libraries, training center), with a focus on culture and heritage policies, and a strong interest for IT applied to edition and librarianship. She also taught history and cultural heritage management at Université Toulouse – Jean Jaurès, and managed research and publishing at Ecole nationale des Chartes. She's been head of La Rochelle Université library before joining PSL, where she supports libraries cooperation and open science development.

E-mail address: sylvie.fayet@psl.eu

Óscar Corcho, UPM

Full professor at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and co-leads the Ontology Engineering Group

Óscar Corcho is full professor at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and co-leads the Ontology Engineering Group. His research activities are focused on the Semantic Web and the Web of Linked Data, Ontological Engineering and the application of semantic technologies to different domains, such as Open Science. In all of these areas, he combines foundational and applied research. In the area of Open Science, Oscar has participated in the EOSC FAIR working group, where the EOSC Interoperability Framework was created, and has led the EOSC-A Task Force on Semantic Interoperability. He participates in multiple projects related to the implementation of Open Science policies inside institutions (e.g., UPM) and across research communities.

E-mail address: ocorcho@fi.upm.es

Lorenzo Bartalesi, SNS

Associate Professor at SNS, SNS Rector's Delegates for International Relations

Lorenzo Bartalesi is Associate Professor at the Scuola Normale Superiore in Pisa. He was Junior Fellow at the Institut d'études avancées d'Aix-Marseille Université (IMÉRA) and Visiting Fellow at the Freie Universität Berlin and the Centre for Research in the Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities (CRASSH) at the University of Cambridge. From 2016 to 2018, he was Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research Fellow at EHESS Paris. In his research and publications, Lorenzo Bartalesi participates in establishing and developing the "Anthropology of aesthetics", a transdisciplinary field of study concerned with the role of the aesthetic in the processes of creation and transmission of knowledge, practices, beliefs and representations. His publications include the volumes *Histoire naturelle de l'esthétique* (Paris 2021), *Antropologia dell'estetico* (Milano 2017) and the articles *Aesthetic preferences: An evolutionary approach* (2016) and *From the aesthetic mind to the human cultures* (2019). Since 2021 he has been SNS

Rector's Delegates for International Relations and Placement and Leader of Work Package "Disciplinary Broadening" of the "European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA). Horizon 2020 Expert evaluator and SNS Representative for the European Commission Program "New European Bauhaus", he has a particular interest in Open Science issues: he is member of the Academic Committee of SNS for the Development of Open Science and Associate editor of the open-access-diamond journal "Aisthesis".

E-mail lorenzo.bartalesi@sns.it

The Network of OS Ambassadors has an online presence as well

[Link to the page](#)

Upon their successful appointment, the ambassadors took on the responsibility of crafting a detailed work plan, setting the stage for a strategic rollout of outreach initiatives. This careful planning ensures that all efforts are aligned with the overarching goals of the network, facilitating effective communication and engagement within the community. The specifics of this work plan are outlined in the following section, which details the structured approach and the targeted actions the ambassadors will undertake to foster an inclusive and collaborative research environment.

8. Work Plan for Implementing Outreach Actions

The **work plan** was developed based on the action outlines provided by the ambassadors within the EELISA consortium. Each partner, through their ambassadors, contributed a specific action outline, ensuring a collaborative approach to addressing our shared tasks. This integration of Open Science practices into our research and education activities is unified and strategic. The tables below (Table 6-Table 9) present the actions planned, the timeline for execution throughout 2024, the level of implementation at both the partner and EELISA levels, and the targets, indicators, and expected results for these initiatives.

The work plan aims to foster OS practices to build trust, enhance collaboration and information sharing, and encourage researchers to integrate OS principles into their work. The implementation plan for outreach is strategically organized into four key tasks (T), each dedicated to promoting the principles and practices of Open Science within our organizations and the EELISA community (refer to Figure 6). Each of these tasks has successfully produced specific outcomes.

Figure 6. Presentation of the OS Ambassadors work plan components

Connect and Collaborate (T1): This foundational task is centered around establishing and maintaining consistent interactions through a series of events and activities designed to sustain a dynamic discourse on Open Science. This ongoing engagement not only enriches academic dialogue but also strengthens relationships and fosters collaboration across the alliance.

Task 1 is the most active, and comprises a total of 18 planned activities. These activities focus on establishing and maintaining interactions through workshops, mutual learning exercises, and community participation. Key events include a workshop on recognizing OS best practices, a mutual learning exercise on OS adoption, and various online and in-person events designed to promote OS practices. The activities are set to occur throughout 2024 and aim to foster a dynamic discourse on OS, strengthen relationships, and facilitate collaboration across the alliance. Indicators of success include the number of OS excellence diplomas awarded, the number of participants, and the completion of strategic documents and platforms.

Represent and Advocate (T2): As a critical function within our network of Open Science ambassadors, this task strives to forge a cohesive voice on pivotal issues, reflecting the collective stance of the alliance.

Task 2 encompasses 17 activities, highlighting its critical role in forging a cohesive voice on OS issues. This task involves initiatives such as participating in national chapters and working groups, organizing dissemination events, and holding academic open archive commission meetings. These actions are designed to ensure that the collective stance of the alliance is well-represented and that key OS themes, such as data sharing and ethical standards, are addressed. The success indicators include the number of activities and events participated in, the number of attendees, and the implementation of COARA commitments.

Dialogue and Persuade (T3): This task entails engaging in open and strategic communication to influence both internal stakeholders within the alliance and external entities.

Task 3 consists of 16 activities, focusing on engaging in strategic communication to influence internal and external stakeholders. Activities include managing transformative agreements, creating and updating web pages and FAQs on OS, organizing workshops and discussion forums, and recording OS-relevant sessions. This task aims to shape perceptions and advocate for OS adoption through persuasive dialogue and informed discourse. The indicators of success are the number of attendees, feedback received, and the number of recorded sessions and visualizations.

Train and Empower (T4): Dedicated to the development of talent and skills, this task prioritizes educational actions that enhance the capabilities of university members, aligning them with the goals of the alliance. Task 4 is dedicated to developing talent and skills, with 19 activities planned. These activities include courses on research data and software management, workshops on academic writing and OS tools, and training sessions on communication, collaboration, and innovation. The goal is to enhance the capabilities of university members, aligning them with the alliance's objectives. Indicators of success include the number of courses

and attendees, feedback surveys, and statistics on OA articles published before and after the training.

Many of the activities have an **EELISA dimension**, emphasizing the collaborative effort across the network. For example, workshops, mutual learning exercises, and participation in the EELISA Open Science community are designed to engage multiple partners and ensure a unified approach to OS practices. Activities such as the "Love Data Week" events and the "Champions in Open Science Series" further highlight the EELISA-wide engagement.

All activities planned for Q1 and Q2 have been successfully implemented. These early efforts have laid a solid foundation for ongoing engagement and the further implementation of Open Science practices throughout the year.

Table 6. T1 Actions - Connect and Collaborate

Actions	Timeline Q1-Q4 2024	Level of implementation (partner level/ EELISA)	Targets/ Indicators/Expected results
<p>Workshop: Recognition of OS best practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: reward the OS scientists for making efforts toward embedding OS in their research life cycle - create a rewarding system for encouraging the adoption of OS 	Q4, 2024	EELISA	Number of OS excellence diplomas awarded in each institution and at EELISA level
<p>Mutual learning exercise: How OS adoption progresses?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: sharing experiences and learning from each other - each partner will bring examples from his/her institution 	Q3, 2024	EELISA	Number of EELISA participants
<p>Workshop “Data Spaces for Researchers: Fostering Collaborative Research and Innovation”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: explore Open Science practices in EELISA universities. - As an additional scenario, we will explore how to interoperate the data from EELISA data repositories. 	Q1, 2024	EELISA	Final report
<p>Participation in the EELISA Open Science community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -goal: participation in the activities of the Open Science community 	Q2, Q3,Q4 2024	EELISA	Number of meetings
<p>Learn from OS researchers’ experience- online event –inviting open scientists & interested audiences (ex. Live broadcasting on EELISA”’s LinkedIn webpage)</p>	Q1, Q3 2024	EELISA	Number of attendees
<p>New researchers’ welcome day: management and valorization of open-access archives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: provide information to better understand the importance and use of open-access archives 	Q1, 2024 Q4, 2024	SSSA Library	Number of attendees. Statistics on the number of archived documents on IRIS.
<p>Open Science strategic plan</p>	Q3, 2024	UPM	Strategic plan document

<p>-goal: A proposal for implementing Open Science in UPM</p> <p>- This plan will be based and aligned on the work developed in the project EELISA InnoCORE (and following their recommendations)</p>			
<p>Open Science website</p> <p>-goal: A proposal for implementing Open Science in UPM</p> <p>- This website will contain a collection of Open Science resources (guidelines, videos, etc.) to UPM community, as well as news related with Open Science practices in the university. It will be the contact point for the OS Ambassador Network.</p>	Q3, 2024	UPM	Website online
<p>PSL Open Data Platform</p> <p>PSL is presently working on an open research data platform, to be launched by the end of 2024. A network gathering librarians, archivists, researchers, IT specialists and engineers is to be developed to support the inception of best practices for FAIR data, and to help in sharing and downloading datasets.</p>	Q4, 2024	PSL	A functional platform
<p>Open science barometer</p> <p>https://explore.psl.eu/fr/se-former/publier/barometre-de-la-science-ouverte-de-luniversite-psl</p> <p>This tool measures the rate of open access among scientific papers published over the last years by PSL authors in peer-reviewed journals.</p> <p>Such a gauge helps to highlight the shared effort for open access, and to trigger outreach plans if the rate decreases.</p>	Q4, 2024	PSL	Rate of open access among scientific papers published yearly
<p>Collaborative, jointly promoted events as part of Love Data Week February 12-16, 2024</p> <p>- scope: raise awareness on research data management and open data</p>	Q1, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
<p>Request data via web interfaces</p> <p>- scope: Introduction to the basics of REST using selected tools and practical examples</p>	Q1, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants

Data collection using the example of web scraping - scope: why should a researcher know about web scraping? What tools are available to perform web scraping? What can researchers do with this data?	Q1, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
UB Digitisation Centre - scope: insights into how the University Library's holdings are digitised and presented Open Access	Q1, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
Insight into NFDI consortia (e.g. NFDI4Energy) for subject-specific research data management - scope: in-dept overview on developments inside NFDI from participating researchers for all interested people at FAU and it's clinic	Q1, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
Ontology-based data collection (e.g. WissKI) - scope: making data in digital humanities sustainable.	Q1, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
Organizing the event “Open Science in EU projects” - scope: talking about OS principles and practices to raise the level of understanding of what OS is and to implement them in EU projects proposal	Q3, 2024	SNS	% attendees of the total number of post doc fellows/researchers
Organizing the event “Sharing OS PhD experiences as open scientists” - scope: raise awareness of young researchers and advocate the benefits of being an open scientist	Q4, 2024 Q4, 2024	SNS EELISA	Number of attendees from SNS and the network EELISA

Table 7. T2: Represent and Advocate

Actions	Timeline Q1-Q4 2023 & 2024	Level of implementation (partner level/ EELISA)	Targets/ Indicators/Expected results
<p>“FAU support services for Open Science” to talk about the OS definition, the confirmatory research process, OS practices, and in-depth information on open access, OER, open source / open hardware as well as open data</p>	<p>Q1, 2024 Q3, 2024</p>	<p>FAU</p>	<p>Number of participants</p>
<p>“My way” – sharing OS Ambassador’s experience as an open scientist to raise awareness of young researchers and advocate the benefits of being an open scientist</p>	<p>Q2, 2024 Q3, 2024</p>	<p>FAU SSSA UNSPB EELISA</p>	<p>Number of participants</p>
<p>Participation at the activities of the national chapter and working groups - goal: networking and cooperating with other Italian institutions part of COARA - SSSA participates in WGs and Tasks related to thematic workshop organization, translation of the Agreement in Italian, engagement and dissemination, coordination of institutional roadmaps et al.</p>	<p>Q1-Q4, 2024</p>	<p>SSSA</p>	<p>Number of activities in which SSSA participated</p>
<p>Cooperation with COARA’s working groups - goal: to engage with COARA’s international coalition and participate in the activities of selected WGs, also acting as a representative of the national chapter if needed</p>	<p>Q1-Q4, 2024</p>	<p>SSSA</p>	<p>Number of events in which SSSA participated</p>

<p>Working together with SSSA governance to implement COARA's commitments</p> <p>-goal: develop and implement an institutional roadmap to plan the implementation of COARA's commitment</p>	Q1-Q4, 2024	SSSA	Number of commitments implemented
<p>Organization of dissemination event on COARA and OS in Pisa with UNIPI and SNS, in cooperation with the Italian National Chapter</p> <p>- goal: engage the local community at all levels (PhD students, research fellows, administrative staff, faculty and the general public) to raise awareness on COARA and its link with Open Science goals</p>	Q1, 2024	SSSA, SNS	Number of attendees
<p>ITU Academic Open Archive Commission Meetings The first was held on December 1, 2023. There are two meetings planned in 2024. The number may increase according to need</p> <p>-goal: To share current developments and future plans about ITU; Receiving feedback and expectations regarding the open science action plan for the current and coming years</p>	ITU		Publication of ITU open science policy; Publication of the second revised version of the ITU open academic archives directive; Publication of ITU research data management directive; Becoming a member of COARA
<p>Library Week Activities: Wikimarathon (March 25 , 2024)</p>	Q1,2024	ITU	Number of attendees
<p>Library Week Activities: Talk on open culture, invited speaker: Sinan Canan March (29 , 2024)</p>	Q1,2024	ITU	Number of attendees
<p>Library Week Activities: A panel on the philosophy of open science (The date is not yet known, it will be during library week)</p>	Q1,2024	ITU	Number of attendees
<p>Library Open Science Awareness Series: 3. Overview of the European Open Science Cloud (Speaker will be a Horizon Europe National Contact Point, Confirmation is expected for April)</p> <p>Scope: A general information will be given about the European open access cloud and basic information about its services will be shared.</p>	Q2, 2024	ITU	Number of attendees

<p>Library Open Science Awareness Series: 4. We are fighting against fake information together with Wikipedia volunteers. (April 16, 2024, face to face)</p> <p>Scope: Culture of openness, Wikipedia's place in this culture, ways to combat fake information</p>	Q2, 2024	In cooperation with ITU Library & Türkiye Wikimedia Community User Group	Number of attendees
<p>Library Open Science Awareness Series: 5. Creative Commons - Licensing 101 (may 14, 2024, Zoom)</p> <p>Scope: What is an open license, what does it do, what license types are there in CC and for what purposes are they used, what are the tools offered by CC?</p>	Q2, 2024	In cooperation with ITU Library & Creative Commons Türkiye Community	Number of attendees
<p>International Open Access Week Activities (October 21-27, 2024, Activities will be designed according to the determined theme of the week. The theme has not been announced yet.)</p> <p>Scope: "Open Access Week is an opportunity to come together, take action, and raise awareness of the benefits of sharing knowledge openly." as stated on the open access week webpage.</p>	Q4, 2024	ITU	Number of activities and number of attendees
<p>For-EU Lib Open Science Subgroup Meetings (November 14, 2023)</p> <p>Scope: Discuss/identify possible joint activities with all European university alliances on open science</p>	Q4, 2023 Q4	ITU EELISA	Developing a shared understanding of open science within existing European university alliances / Number of joint activities to be carried out by the end of the year
<p>EELISA Open Science Community "Champions in Open Science Series"</p> <p>EELISA Open Science Community Activities Planning</p> <p>EELISA Open Science Community "Open science awareness and expectations survey for early career researchers"</p> <p>Scope: To carry out awareness studies and provide information in accordance with the expectations of EELISA open science community members and EELISA's open science vision.</p>	Q4, 2023- Q4,2004 Q1, 2024 Q2, 2024	ITU EELISA	Number of activities and number of attendees Number of planned activities realized Number of respondents / survey analysis and evaluation report

<p>Workshop – discussing the current FAU OS practices within the Open Access Week 2024 (Oct. 21st to 27th, 2024)</p> <p>- scope: raise the level of understanding of what OS is and what can we do to adopt OS practices.</p>	Q3, 2024	FAU	Number of participants
<p>Workshop – „From writing to OA publishing” at the Long Night of the Sciences</p> <p>-scope : Insight into non-commercial Open Access publishers such as university presses, publication preparation and process in Word or LaTeX, copyrights, Creative Commons licences</p>	Q2, 2024	FAU	Number of participants
<p>Long Night of Writing campaign</p> <p>- scope: provide support to students to enhance their ability to write term papers and academic theses</p>	Q1, 2024	FAU	Number of participants
<p>Participation at the activities of the National Chapter and Working Groups</p> <p>- scope: networking and cooperating with other Italian institutions part of COARA (SNS participates in CoARA Task Force 1.2 of the National Chapter related to coordination of institutional roadmaps)</p>	Q1-Q4, 2024	SNS Research Assessment and OS Service	Number of activities in which SNS participated
<p>Working together with SNS governance to implement COARA’s commitments</p> <p>- scope: develop and implement an institutional roadmap to plan the implementation of COARA’s commitment</p>	Q1-Q4, 2024	SNS Research Assessment and OS Service	Number of commitments planned in the roadmap
<p>Organization of dissemination event on COARA and OS in Pisa with UNIPI and SSSA, in cooperation with the Italian National Chapter</p> <p>- scope: engage the local community at all levels (PhD students, research fellows, administrative staff, faculty and the general public) to raise awareness on COARA and its link with Open Science goals</p>	Q1, 2024	SNS Research Assessment and OS Service	Number of attendees to the dissemination event on COARA and OS in Pisa

Table 8. T3 Actions: Dialogue & Persuade

Actions	Timeline Q1-Q4 2024	Level of implementation (partner level/ EELISA)	Targets/ Indicators/Expected results
<p>Management of transformative agreements; communication and awareness of these tools towards the academic community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: provide information to better understand the terms and conditions for publishing in OS; - support and assistance to authors for publication. 	<p>Q4, 2023 Q4, 2024</p>	<p>SSSA Library</p>	<p>Number of attendees of information sessions Number of articles published through transformative agreements</p>
<p>Creation and updating of web pages dedicated to practices, tools and regulations regarding open access and open science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: raise awareness of young researchers about OS practices - provide tools for author's OA publishing workflow 	<p>Q1, 2024 Q4, 2024</p>	<p>SSSA Library</p>	<p>Number of visualizations and feedbacks received, considering the number/type of published contents</p>
<p>Preparation of videos in Italian and English regarding the OS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: raise awareness of young researchers about OS practices 	<p>Q2, 2024</p>	<p>SSSA Library</p>	<p>Number of visualizations feedbacks received</p>
<p>Creation of FAQs on Open Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: help resolve concerns about open science practices 	<p>Q4, 2024</p>	<p>SSSA Library</p>	<p>Number of feedbacks received</p>
<p>Organizing the event “Open Science Explained”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -goal: talking about OS principles, OS movement, OS-related organizations, and raise the level of understanding of what OS is and what can we do to adopt OS practices. 	<p>Q1, 2024</p>	<p>SSSA UNSTPB</p>	<p>% attendees of the total number of researchers</p>

- Why should I become an open scientist? – arguments/benefits			
Workshop – discussing the current OS practices - goal: raise the level of understanding of what OS is and what can we do to adopt OS practices.	Q2, 2024 Q4, 2024	UNSTPB	number of new OS researchers – to be compared and the end of the year with the existing ones
Workshop – Open Access Day -goal : create opportunities for discussions and acquiring information to increase Romanian researchers visibility	Q1, 2024	UNSTPB	Number of participants
Create a discussion forum on OS challenges and barriers - goal: identifying what are the drivers of change and what are the researchers' concerns and fear to help them overcome it	Q2, 2024	UNSTPB	Analysis of posts will offer deeper insights into how OS can be promoted efficiently
Enhance collaboration and trust -goal: create opportunities for researchers to meet peers from other EELISA partners	Q2, 2024 Q4, 2024	EELISA	Number of attendees and the end of 2024, number of publications in co-authorship with EELISA peers
Workshop: Recognition of OS best practices -goal: reward the OS scientists for making efforts toward embedding OS in their research life cycle - create a rewarding system for encouraging the adoption of OS	Q4, 2024	EELISA	Number of OS excellence diplomas awarded in each institution and at EELISA level
Organization of the yearly OS Week goal: talking about OS principles, OS movement, and OS-related organizations Why should I become an open scientist? – arguments/benefits	Q1, 2024	ENPC	% attendees of the total number of researchers
Regular attendance at laboratory Councils -goal: raise awareness on OS practices - advocate the benefits of being an open scientist	Q1, 2024 Q2, 2024 Q3, 2024	ENPC	Number of participation

	Q4, 2024		
Regular drop-in Sessions to engage with researchers - goal: raise the level of understanding of what OS is and what can we do to adopt OS practices.	Q1, 2024 Q2, 2024 Q3, 2024 Q4, 2024	ENPC	Number of intervention
Library Open Science Awareness Series: 1. Open Access Publishing (February 20, 2023 face to face; October 22, 2024 face to face) goal: understand how to publish your work openly and be aware of the advantages; be able to find an OA publisher for your research; to have information about ITU's current open access publishing tools and services	Q1, 2024	ITU Library	Increasing the awareness about open access publishing and informing researchers about existing R&D agreements / Number of attendees/ number of feedback posts
ITU Read & Publish Agreements Information Meetings: ACM Digital Library, Cambridge Core Journals, Oxford Academic Journals Online (February, March, April, May)	Q1, 2024 Q2, 2024	ITU Library & EBSCO	Creating awareness about existing R&D agreements/ Number of attendees
Library Open Science Awareness Series: 2. Predatory publishing in research (March 20, 2024, face to face; November 19, 2024, Face to face)	Q1, 2024	ITU Library	Increasing the awareness about predatory publishers/ Number of attendees/ number of feedback posts
Interview with ITU open science ambassador -goal: Introducing the open science ambassador; Informing ITU members about the role and responsibilities of the OS ambassador; Sharing ways to collaborate with OS ambassador	Q1, 2024	ITU	Publication of the interview with different channels / number of feedbacks and collaboration requests / Collaborations with the Ambassador
Publishing research data - scope: RD definition, arguments for and against data publication, funding for open data, ways to publish data	Q3, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants

(e.g. insights into data journals, data repositories), legal aspects, FAU support services			
Data Management Halloween Escape Room - scope: fight a way out of a Data Horror Escape Room and learn about research data management in the process	Q4, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
Create a discussion forum on OS challenges and barriers - scope: identifying what are the drivers of change and what are the researchers' concerns and fear to help them overcome it	Q2, 2024	FAU	Analysis of posts will offer deeper insights into how OS can be promoted efficiently
Recording of OS-relevant sessions -scope: record lectures, workshops and exercises whenever legally and by the speakers feasible, in order to offer these videos more frequently, even outside the time capacities of the speakers	Q1-4, 2024	FAU	Number of recorded sessions
Continue to build and expand the members of the EELISA Open Science Community -scope: there must be many more FAU members interested in OS, these need to be identified and encouraged to get involved or at least participate in the EELISA Open Science Community	Q1-4, 2024	FAU	Number of EELISA OSC members
New researchers welcome day: management and valorization of open-access archives - scope: provide information to better understand the importance and use of open-access archives	Q4, 2024	SNS Research Assessment and OS Service	Number of attendees. Statistics on the number of archived documents on IRIS.
Transformative agreements: creation and updating of web pages dedicated to transformative agreements to increase the awareness of these tools towards the academic community	Q1, 2024	SNS Library	Number of articles published through transformative agreements

- scope: provide information to better understand the terms and conditions for publishing in OS; - support and assistance to authors for publication			
Creation and updating of web pages dedicated to practices, tools and regulations regarding open access and open science - scope: raise awareness of young researchers about OS practices - provide tools for author's OA publishing workflow	Q1-Q4, 2024	SNS Research Assessment and OS Service	Number of visualizations and feedbacks received, considering the number/type of published contents
Preparation of videos in Italian regarding Zotero tool, to manage and share bibliography - scope: raise awareness of young researchers about OS practice	Q1, 2024	SNS Library	Number of visualizations and feedbacks received

Table 9. T4 Actions - Train & Empower

Actions	Timeline Q1-Q4 2024	Level of implementation (partner level/ EELISA)	Targets/ Indicators/Expected results
Research Data Management course - goal: training UPM community (researchers / PhD students) in research data management. These courses will be organized by the International Doctoral School. - They will learn how to publish their data in Zenodo and how to create a DMP	Q2/Q3, 2024	UPM	Number of courses + Number of attendees
Research Software Management course	Q2/Q3, 2024	UPM	Number of courses + Number of attendees

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: training UPM community (researchers / PhD students) in research software management. These courses will be organized by the International Doctoral School. - They will learn how to publish their software, selecting the appropriated license and manage their lifecycle using control version systems. 			
<p>Workshop – Academic Writing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: provide training to young researchers to enhance their ability to write academic papers and publish in prestigious journals 	Q1, 2024	SSSA	R1-R2 researchers
<p>Open Publishing - what do you need to know?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: provide information on open publication practices and guidelines - why should I publish in OA journals? What is in for me? 	Q2, 2024	SSSA	Statistics on the number of OA articles published before and after (2024 compared with previous years)
<p>Workshop: Open Science tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -goal: setting the scene for the change- presenting OS tools available and explaining how to use them 	Q4, 2024	SSSA	Number of attendees that are using OS tools (next year)
<p>Training session: Open Science and Innovation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -goal: start a series of training sessions for researchers interested in Open Science and Open Innovation 	Q1, 2024	SSSA	Feedback survey to assess the impact of the training session
<p>PhD course about Open Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: provide young researchers (PhD) the tools and standards required to embed Open Science in research workflows 	Q1	SSSA	Number of attendees
<p>Workshop: Publishing solutions for research papers and support for selection process of scientific journals in Romania</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal: raise awareness on publishing options and journals selection process 	Q4, 2023	UNSTPB	Number of attendees

Online training session – Enformation & UPB <i>Electronic access to scientific literature to support and promote Romanian research and education system</i>	Q4.2023	UNSTPB	Number of attendees (R1-R4 researchers)
Online training session series : How to benefit the most of EBSCO Host? -goal: train researchers to use the EBSCO Host platform, find relevant literature, authors search Available on: 1, 7 and 22 nov. 2023	Q4, 2023	UNSTPB	Number of online participants
Online training session series: Understand what the SciVal platform is offering Available on 29 nov., 5 and 7 dec 2023	Q4, 2023	UNSTPB	Number of online participants
SciVal for research performance analysis November 23, 2023	Q4, 2023	UNSTPB & Elsevier	Number of participants
Workshop – Academic Writing - goal: provide training to young researchers to enhance their ability to write academic papers and publish in prestigious journals	Q1, 2024	UNSTPB	R1-R2 researchers
Open Publishing - what do you need to know? - goal: provide information on open publication practices and guidelines - why should I publish in OA journals? What is in for me?	Q2, 2024	UNSTPB	Statistics on the number of OA articles published before and after (2024 compared with previous years)
Training session: Open Science and Innovation -goal: start a series of training sessions for researchers interested in Open Science and Open Innovation	Q1, 2024	UNSTPB ENPC	Feedback survey to assess the impact of the training session
Training session: Communication and collaboration - goal: advice researchers on how to communicate with peers, initiate collaboration, build trust, and protect IPR	Q2, 2024	UNSTPB	Number of attendees compared with the number of collaboration agreements issued

Webinar- Basic Elements of TÜBİTAK ULAKBİM + WILEY Free Open Access Article Publishing Agreement and Latest Developments in Open Access Publishing (Nov 14, 2023 10:00 AM - 11:00 AM)	Q3, 2024	In cooperation with ITU & TUBITAK/ULAKBİM	Creating awareness about new R&P agreements/ Number of open access publications to be made within the goal of Wiley R&P agreement
Webinar - Publishing successful academic articles in Wiley journals: Some important details from our editor! (Nov 13, 2023 12:00 PM - 2:00 PM) -Goal: understanding the nature of R&P agreements and knowledge of current developments in open access publishing	Q3, 2024	In cooperation with ITU & TUBITAK/ULAKBİM	Creating awareness about new R&P agreements/ Number of open access publications to be made within the goal of Wiley R&P agreement
Open Educational Resources Workshop: Discover, Plan, Develop! Scope: open educational resource framework ; How can OER be used in lessons? How can open educational resources be developed?	Q3, 2024	ITU	Number of attendees
Online training session series : „Metadaten” (in English: metadata; videos in German only) - scope: introduction to the field of metadata for research data; various aspects of the different types and schemas are shown Rerun of the video series in a public session	Q2, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
Online training session series : "Forschungssoftware & Datenformate" (in English: research software & data Formats; videos in German only) - scope: presentation of digital tools and software that can significantly support research projects, especially for humanities and social science researchers Rerun of the video series in a public session	Q2, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
Online training session series : "Forschungsdaten suchen & nachnutzen" (in English: search and reuse research data; videos in German only)	Q2, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scope: finding relevant research data repositories, checking the technical reusability of data, legal aspects of reuse, data citation <p>Rerun of the video series in a public session</p>			
<p>Online training session series : "Forschungsdaten & Datenmanagementplan" (in English: research data and data management plan; videos in German only)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scope: presentation of the data management plan tool "RDMO" and description of its basic functions. <p>Rerun of the video series in a public session</p>	Q2, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
<p>Using open education resources in teaching:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scope: search, evaluation and use of OER, Creative Commons licences and special OER search tools for use in digital teaching 	Q1, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
<p>Agile methods and open source</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scope: learn agile methods by developing open-source software 	Q1, 2024	FAU	Number of online participants
<p>PhD course about Open Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scope: provide young researchers (PhD) the tools and standards required to embed Open Science in research workflows 	Q1, 2024	SNS Research Assessment and Open Science Service	Number of attendees
<p>Workshop – Academic Writing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scope: provide training to young researchers to enhance their ability to write academic papers and publish in prestigious journals 	Q2, 2024	SNS Teaching Activities Service	Number of PhD students
<p>Open Publishing - what do you need to know?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scope: provide information on open publication practices and guidelines - why should I publish in OA journals? What is in for me? 	Q1, 2024	SNS Research Assessment and OS Service	Statistics on the number of OA articles published before and after (2024 compared with previous years)

9. Dissemination and sustainability activities

Communication of the OS Network

In September 2023, the EELISA Network of Open Science (OS) Ambassadors page was launched to facilitate communication and dissemination of the Network's initiatives.

To spread the news about the network and enhance visibility, we have run several communication actions, particularly leveraging social media platforms. These actions include:

- **Homepage Launch:** The dedicated homepage for the EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors provides comprehensive information about the network's goals, activities, and members. It acts as a resource center for anyone interested in Open Science initiatives within EELISA (refer to Figure 7).
- **Social Media Campaigns:** To maximize outreach, we utilized various social media platforms:
 - *Posts on X (formerly Twitter):* Regular updates and announcements about the network were shared on X, engaging the academic and research community (refer to Figure 8, [link to the page](#)).
 - **Posts on Instagram:** Visual content and stories about the network's activities were posted on Instagram, appealing to a broad audience and encouraging interaction ([link to the page](#)).
 - **Posts on LinkedIn:** Professional updates, articles, and events related to the OS Ambassadors were shared on LinkedIn, targeting researchers, academics, and professionals in the field. ([link to the page](#)).

Figure 7. The homepage of the EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors

Figure 8. Post on social media about the Network

The latest of the array of activities around this subject is the launching of the [#OpenScienceAmbassadors](#) Network 🤗

Would you like to meet the EELISA advocates for this paradigm shift? Click here ➡ lnk.bio/s/eelisa/e5ac9

EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors

Posts on X [Link to the page](#)
Posts on Instagram [Link to the page](#)

EELISA European University
3,970 followers
6mo · Edited · 🌐

Are you familiar with [#OpenScience](#)?

It is a new approach to the scientific process, based on [#cooperation](#) and spreading knowledge through digital technologies and new collaborative tools.

[#EELISA](#) has set [#OpenScience](#) as a key topic for the alliance, implementing a whole array of activities around this subject. The latest of them is the launching of the [#OpenScienceAmbassadors](#) Network.

Would you like to meet them? Click here to meet the EELISA advocates for this paradigm shift: lnk.bio/s/eelisa/e5ac9

[#science](#) [#STEM](#) [#collaboration](#) ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences PSL Research University Istanbul Technical University Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna Scuola Normale Superiore FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg Universidad Politécnica de Madrid University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest Mines Paris Chimie ParisTech - PSL Budapest University of Technology and Economics Ecole des Ponts ParisTech

EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors

You and 24 others · 5 reposts

Reactions

Posts on LinkedIn [Link to the page](#)

- **Video Campaign:** A video was created featuring Ciprian Dobre, the OS ambassador at the University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest, highlighting his role and contributions to the Open Science movement. This video was shared on social media platforms to introduce the OS Ambassadors Network and showcase its groundbreaking work. The video emphasizes the innovative initiatives and collaborative efforts shaping the future of

scientific collaboration within EELISA. [[link to the LinkedIn page](#); [link to the Instagram page](#)]

Figure 9. EELISA OS Network of Ambassadors Video

The dissemination and communication activities have been designed and implemented with the support of EELISA InnoCORE WP.1

These communication actions have significantly contributed to raising awareness about the EELISA Network of Open Science Ambassadors, fostering a collaborative and engaged Open Science community across the alliance.

Leveraging the Open Science Training Hub: A Resource for OS Ambassadors

The Open Science (OS) Training Hub, with its comprehensive course catalog and user-friendly platform architecture, is an invaluable tool for OS Ambassadors within the EELISA network. This resource supports ambassadors in their mission to promote and integrate Open Science practices across partner universities. The OS Training Hub features a distributed architecture, utilizing Moodle instances configured with the eduGAIN access mechanism. This setup allows seamless access to a wide array of Open Science courses hosted by EELISA partners. When a partner university cannot provide a Moodle instance with eduGAIN access, they can host their courses on the UPB platform or other available platforms. Furthermore, some courses are made openly accessible to everyone, not just EELISA affiliates, enhancing the reach of Open Science education.

Figure 10. The homepage of the EELISA Open Science Catalogue

EELISA Open Science Catalogue [Link to the page](#)

The OS Training Hub is a powerful tool for OS Ambassadors, enabling them to effectively promote, educate, and integrate Open Science practices within their institutions and across the EELISA network. By leveraging this platform, ambassadors can enhance the impact of their initiatives and contribute to the broader adoption of Open Science principles.

OS Ambassadors can use the Training Hub to facilitate the dissemination and adoption of Open Science practices by:

1. **Promoting course offerings:** Ambassadors can actively promote the available courses within their institutions and networks, encouraging researchers to engage with the diverse training opportunities. By highlighting specific courses (see Figure 11) relevant to their peers, ambassadors can drive participation and enhance Open Science literacy.

Figure 11. Examples of courses available in the OS Course Catalogue

Research Software Management [Link to the page](#) | Research Data Management courses [Link to the page](#)

2. **Organizing and facilitating workshops:** Using the resources available on the Training Hub, ambassadors can organize workshops and training sessions tailored to their institution's needs. They can leverage the platform's functionalities to track progress, issue completion certificates, and provide access to course materials.
3. **Encouraging collaboration:** The federated access mechanism provided by eduGAIN facilitates collaboration among researchers across different institutions. Ambassadors can use this feature to foster cross-institutional learning and collaboration, promoting a unified approach to Open Science within the EELISA network.
4. **Providing feedback and updates:** The Training Hub is continuously updated with new courses and resources. Ambassadors can contribute by proposing new Open Science courses and training programs through the contact page, ensuring the platform remains current and relevant.
5. **Enhancing engagement through communication:** Ambassadors can use discussion forums and other interactive features of the platform to engage with researchers, share insights, and address queries related to Open Science practices. This interaction helps build a supportive community around Open Science initiatives.

Continuation of the OS Network of Ambassadors under EELISA 2.0

The Open Science (OS) Network of Ambassadors can continue and expand its efforts under the EELISA 2.0 framework by leveraging the possible synergies identified within **WP9: EELISA network for researchers and talent**. The OS Network of Ambassadors will align its activities with the three key tasks outlined in EELISA 2.0 to foster collaborative research support and enhance Open Science practices (refer to Figure 12).

The ongoing EELISA 2.0 project presents an opportunity to develop further new OS mechanism and practices within WP9.

Figure 12. Possible synergies with EELISA 2.0

EELISA 2.0

WP9: EELISA network for researchers and talent

Task 9.1

Joint research-support functions

Task 9.2

Joint research structures and facilities

Task 9.3

Collaborative Open Science mechanisms and offers

Possible synergies

- Development of joint OSAP at the EELISA level
- Enriching the OS framework already developed
- Development of joint mechanisms and practices to enable, incentivize, measure and reward OS practices

Under **Task 9.1**, the OS Network of Ambassadors can contribute to the development of joint research-support functions by integrating Open Science principles into these support mechanisms. Ambassadors can facilitate workshops and training sessions to educate researchers on the benefits of Open Science, ensuring that research-support functions incorporate and promote OS practices. By providing guidance and support, ambassadors can help streamline processes that enable researchers to adopt Open Science more effectively.

For **Task 9.2**, the OS Network of Ambassadors can play a crucial role in the establishment and management of joint research structures and facilities. Ambassadors can help disseminate and potentially develop collaborative research infrastructures that prioritize Open Science. This includes developing shared data repositories, ensuring interoperability of data across institutions, and promoting the use of open-access facilities.

Task 9.3 directly aligns with the core mission of the OS Network of Ambassadors. Under this task, ambassadors can lead the development of joint mechanisms and practices to enable, incentivize, measure, and reward Open Science practices. This includes creating and implementing an Open Science Awards Program at the EELISA level to recognize and reward researchers who excel in Open Science. Ambassadors can also work on enriching the existing OS framework by incorporating feedback and best practices from across the EELISA network. Through these efforts, the network can ensure that Open Science practices are not only adopted but also sustained and incentivized.

This collaborative approach will enhance the research environment, foster innovation, and ensure that Open Science remains a central pillar of the EELISA community.

11. Concluding Remarks

Open Science Ambassadors are instrumental in cultivating an environment characterized by openness, transparency, and collaboration in scientific research. This guide lays out a strategy for the EELISA alliance's universities to effectively enlist and involve these ambassadors, thereby securing the ongoing growth and success of the open science initiative.

In essence, the establishment and flourishing of the EELISA InnoCORE Open Science Ambassadors network rely on more than just the ambassadors themselves. It equally depends on a strong and unique **institutional** and **digital footprint**.

Leveraging **digital tools** to aid the activities of the ambassadors is crucial. In today's digital era, the astute application of technology can simplify communication, boost collaboration, and expand the reach of the network's efforts.

Moreover, enhancing the digital visibility of the **Open Science community** should be at the forefront of our priorities. By establishing a readily accessible and visible digital space, we can enable the community to grow into a powerful learning community. This space will act as a central meeting point for interaction, knowledge sharing, and collective learning, promoting growth, inclusiveness, and ongoing improvement in Open Science practices.

In conclusion, the path forward for maximizing the impact of the EELISA Open Science Ambassadors network, as well as the broader Open Science community, involves cultivating a robust identity, proficient utilization of digital tools, and fostering an engaging digital environment.